

HumanTech News | June 2024

2 years of HumanTech

We're celebrating! 🎉

It's already been **two years** since we embarked on our journey towards boosting the digitalisation of the construction industry with cutting-edge human-centred robotic and AI technologies.

Two years of hard work and outstanding achievements in which we have made significant strides in strengthening our core values: **collaboration**, **innovation** and **scientific excellence**.

- **We have strengthened teamwork** within our [HumanTech team](#), comprised of 21 partners in 10 countries, and across the 8 EU-funded projects involved in our [Tech4EUconstruction cluster](#).
- We have made significant progress in developing our **technologies** and have seen individual results of partners combined into integrated systems that have produced impressive **demonstrators**.
- We have published new **papers** in top-tier conferences, participated in key sector **events**, received recognition through various **awards**, and made **resources** openly available.

We also achieved a key milestone by successfully holding our **[18-month periodic reporting and review](#)**, in which we we received positive feedback from European

Commission reviewers.

We still have a whole year ahead of us with one main challenge: our **pilots**. "We are currently working hard to realise our 5 project pilots, which will be carried out in diverse settings (office buildings, bridges) and countries (Spain, Switzerland, Germany, Singapore) between the end of 2024 and the beginning of 2025", [says our coordinator, Jason Rambach](#).

The future of construction awaits us.
Are you ready?

[Learn more about our progress over the last year](#)

Make sure to follow us on our social channels and, if you haven't already, [subscribe to this newsletter](#) to stay updated.

Now, let's dive into our resources, stories, and inspiration on construction innovation. Enjoy!

HumanTech Resources

Dive into the HumanTech resources!

- Training
- Open source
- Deliverables

Explore our training materials, source code repositories for many of our scientific publications, and public deliverables from the first 18 months of the project to learn more about our work — and stay tuned for upcoming resources!

[TRAINING](#)[OPEN SOURCE](#)[DELIVERABLES](#)

HumanTech Publications

Dive into our latest research papers and articles, and stay updated on our latest developments and insights.

[Single Frame Semantic Segmentation Using Multi-Modal Spherical Images](#)

In recent years, there has been growing interest in panoramic images offering a 360-degree perspective. Our study introduces a **cross-modal fusion architecture to enhance scene analysis**. We use distortion-aware modules to address object deformations and panorama distortions due to equirectangular representation. Additionally, we facilitate cross-modal interactions for feature rectification and information exchange for bi-modal and tri-modal feature streams.

[Learn more](#)

[BRep Boundary and Junction Detection for CAD Reverse Engineering](#)

The machining process involves a crucial step of 3D reverse engineering of mechanical system to obtain parametric CAD models from 3D scans. In this paper, we introduce **BRepDetNet, a neural network for detecting boundaries and junctions in 3D scans from the CC3D and ABC datasets**. The network learns to detect boundaries and junctions by minimizing focal loss and non-maximal suppression during training, and our experimental results show impressive results.

[Learn more](#)

HumanTech Stories

[HumanTech Hackathon: Gabor Sziebig on the benefits of our technologies in construction](#)

We held our first Robotic Integration Hackathon at ACCIONA's construction test site in Madrid. Partners from 6 organisations and 5 countries came together to test and integrate some of the technologies we are developing with one goal: prepare for our technical demonstrations in real construction sites.

Learn about how can these technologies benefit the construction industry and the team behind them in this **interview with Gabor Sziebig**, Research Manager in Robotics and Automation at SINTEF Manufacturing, and stay tuned for more interviews with our partners!

[Learn more](#)

[User evaluation at HumanTech](#)

During the European Robotics Forum, we took the chance to interview our colleagues Patricia Helen Rosen and Sascha Wischniewski from the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA) about our user evaluation work. Check them out:

When developing innovative technology for use in the workplace, it's key to collaborate with on-site experts to identify challenges and improve user acceptance. Learn about our user evaluation work in this interview with **Sascha Wischniewski**.

What do workers think about our HumanTech technologies — from exoskeletons to XR glasses and cobots? Learn about our first worker evaluation results in this interview with **Patricia Helen Rosen**.

HumanTech Work

We recently launched the 'Discover the HumanTech Work' series, in which we are exploring the work packages (WPs) that make up HumanTech with the team members who lead them.

[Wearable technologies for construction](#)

Explore WP4, led by Bruno Walter Mirbach, Senior Researcher at the Department of Augmented Vision at DFKI.

[Human factors – Training, usability and assessment](#)

Delve into WP6, presented by Gloria Callinan, Project Support Officer at the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS).

[Dissemination, communication and exploitation](#)

Learn about WP8, presented by Giulia Pastor and Andrea Torres from AUSTRALO.

[Overall Framework Definitions](#)

Look into WP1, led by DFKI and presented by Jason Rambach.

HumanTech Technologies

At HumanTech, we are achieving major breakthroughs in cutting-edge technologies. We have asked three of our colleagues, **Hideaki Kanayama** (RICOH), **Mahdi Chamseddine** (DFKI) and **Markus Miezal** (Sci-track), to give us the key details of some of them: our 360° ToF camera, scan to BIM, and visual-inertial tracking unit technologies — which are set to transform how construction sites are monitored and managed.

[Discover our 360° ToF camera](#)

[Learn about our scan to BIM technology.](#)

[Explore the keys to our visual-inertial tracking unit](#)

HumanTech Events

Over the past months, our HumanTech team has participated in numerous events worldwide:

- The international conference in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR2024) — the most important computer vision event worldwide — in Seattle, [where Jason Rambach \(DFKI\) presented our 3rd-place winning method](#) of the Scan-to-BIM.
- The Construction Health & Safety Summit 2024 in Ireland, where Gloria Callinan (TUS) represented HumanTech in the panel discussion: ['Constructing the future: The AI revolution in the construction industry'](#). Patricia Helen Rosen (BAuA) shared her knowledge of the intersection between technology use and worker well-being in the session ['Considering human factors to create safe and healthy workplaces'](#).

The logo features a stylized red graphic on the left consisting of three vertical bars of increasing height, followed by a cloud-like shape. To the right of this graphic, the text "SUSTAINABLE PLACES 2024" is displayed in a bold, sans-serif font. "SUSTAINABLE" and "PLACES" are in black, while "2024" is in red.

SUSTAINABLE PLACES 2024

In September, we will participate in the [Sustainable Places Conference](#) in Luxembourg, Europe's first destination for EU research collaboration and market opportunities!

We are organising a workshop to explore the intersection of sustainable construction and renovation together with our [Tech4EUconstruction cluster](#) members: BEEYONDERS, RoBétArmé, Reincarnate, and InCUBE.

It focuses on digital twins, machine-human collaboration, and sustainable materials, and aims to facilitate networking and foster synergies, addressing challenges such as sustainable materials, skilled workforce, and waste management.

 From 23th to 25th September 2024

[Check out the agenda](#)

[Explore the latest in our
Tech4EUconstruction cluster](#)

THE SCIENCE BEHIND CONSTRUCTION
GREEN AND SMART INNOVATIONS

humantech

BEEYONDERS

ROBETARME

REINCARNATE

InCUBE

BIMTWIN

Reconmatic

Heron

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We have compiled 30 scientific publications alongside projects from the Tech4EUConstruction Cluster and will soon start sharing them on our social channels.

This campaign will showcase the cluster's advancements in construction and engineering and the science behind innovations in **building renovation, sustainability monitoring, digital innovation technologies, energy efficiency, renewable energy, and materials and design.**

[How can we realise a digitally controlled circular construction?](#) | This article compiles 8 research developments achieved by REINCARNATE, published in BUILD UP, the European portal for energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings.

[Sustainability and circularity indicators in construction](#) | Check the steps taken by RECONMATIC to define the indicators of circularity and sustainability in the construction sector, which they will feed into an assessment tool.

To finish, one last recommendation

 [Hard Fork](#), a podcast from The New York Times, hosted by journalists Kevin Roose and Casey Newton.

It covers the latest stories in tech and features news and discussions related

to AI.

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

Get in touch

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